

STANDARDIZED DOCUMENTATION FOR VERIFICATION, VALIDATION, AND ACCREDITATION (VV&A) — HELPING ASSURE MISSION SUCCESS

Kevin Charlow, David Broyles
Space and Naval Warfare Systems Center Charleston
Charleston, SC

Curtis Blais
MOVES Institute, Naval Postgraduate School
Monterey, CA

Marcy Stutzman
Northrop Grumman Corporation
Laurel, MD

ABSTRACT

The Department of Defense (DoD) Modeling and Simulation Steering Committee's Acquisition Community Lead sponsors the project, "Standardized Documentation for Verification, Validation, and Accreditation (VV&A)." This paper will update the military communications and information processing community on that project. It will provide information about MIL-STD-3022, which recommends standardized content and format requirements for four core VV&A documents; the DoD VV&A Documentation Tool, which is the technology that automates the production of the four VV&A documents to ensure standardization across the DoD and Military Departments; and the development of VV&A XML schemas that enable the sharing of VV&A information via the Global Information Grid enterprise anywhere in the world and at anytime.

INTRODUCTION

The Military Communications (MILCOM) community is concerned with communications and information processing systems technologies and capabilities that assure mission success by addressing the 21st century challenges of national defense, homeland security, and disaster response. The reader might wonder what roles Modeling and Simulation (M&S) Verification, Validation, and Accreditation (VV&A) play in helping to assure mission success. This paper will inform the community about VV&A data and architecture products that will provide capabilities for producers to document confidence in using M&S to inform decisions important for military communications and for consumers to find information about reusable MILCOM M&S that have undergone VV&A.

The paper will begin with a brief background description of the Department of Defense (DoD) M&S Project titled,

Standardized Documentation for VV&A. We will discuss the concept of operations and then focus on the project's products that can be used to help assure mission success. Specifically, the paper will address:

- Policy, guidance, and standards
 - Military Standard (MIL-STD) 3022
 - DoD Directive (DoDD) 5000.59
 - DoD Instruction (DoDI) 5000.61
- Roles
 - Producer
 - Consumer
- Data
 - Sharing DoD Community content data
 - M&S Community of Interest (COI)
 - VV&A Extensible Markup Language (XML) metadata
 - Exposing authoritative VV&A document data
- Architecture
 - DoD VV&A Documentation Tool (DVDT) services architecture
 - Leveraging services (What do I need? Who has it? How do I get it?)
 - Sharing across MILCOM domains (Sea, Land, Air, and Space)

PROJECT BACKGROUND

DoDI 5000.61, *DoD M&S VV&A* [1], sets policy requiring accreditation of all models and simulations. Since 1996, organizations across DoD have been implementing VV&A processes and documenting VV&A information. Guidance for implementing VV&A comes in the form of DoD-, Service- and organizational-level instructions, recommended practices, guidebooks, handbooks, and standards. The requirements for documenting VV&A information vary from Service-to-Service, organization-to-organization, and community-to-community, although all

require the same basic types of information needed for gaining confidence in the application of M&S results for an intended use.

As this paper is being written, the M&S Steering Committee (M&S SC) is conducting a review of DoDI 5000.61 for the purposes of updating the instruction to reflect changes in M&S management and making other necessary administrative updates.

In 2007, DoDD 5000.59, *DoD M&S Management* [2], formally established the M&S SC, an executive-level DoD committee comprising Senior Executive Service, flag or general officers of the military, or officials of equivalent rank and precedence. The initial membership included the Under Secretary of Defense for Acquisition, Technology and Logistics; Under Secretary of Defense for Policy; the Under Secretary of Defense for Personnel and Readiness; the Director of Program Analysis and Evaluation; the Director of Operational Test and Evaluation; the Military Secretaries; the Chairman of the Joint Chiefs of Staff; and the Commander of U.S. Joint Forces Command. The purpose for the M&S SC is to govern, guide, and oversee matters relating to DoD M&S management. The membership represents five DoD Communities enabled by M&S. Those communities include Acquisition, Analysis, Planning, Testing, Training, and Experimentation.

This project is sponsored by the DoD Acquisition Community Lead, the Deputy Director for Developmental Test and Evaluation in the Office of the Under Secretary of Defense for Acquisition, Technology & Logistics, who provides direct oversight.

Figure 1. Project Organization

Figure 1 depicts the project's organization. The project is organized into four teams: (1) a Project Management Team led by Team Manager, Kevin Charlow; (2) a Policy,

Guidance & Standards Team led by Marcy Stutzman; (3) a Taxonomy & Metadata Team led by Curtis Blais; and (4) an Architecture & Software Development Team led by David Broyles.

The Team Manager reports to the Acquisition M&S Working Group, the M&S Integrated Process Team, the M&S SC, and the M&S Coordination Office (M&S CO).

In 2007, the M&S Technical Review Group (led by M&S CO) for M&S Standards processed through the Defense Standardization Program reviewed and commented on a draft document comprising four draft VV&A document templates: the Accreditation Plan, Verification and Validation (V&V) Plan, V&V Report, and Accreditation Report. A comment resolution team then adjudicated all comments that were submitted. All adjudicated essential comments received approval from the individual submitters and the draft standard was updated accordingly. In January 2008, MIL-STD-3022 [3] (Figure 2) was approved by the Defense Standardization Program as a DoD Standard Practice, and as such, may be cited as a solicitation requirement.

Figure 2. MIL-STD-3022

Additionally, Data Item Descriptions (DIDs) are available for the VV&A documents as follows:

- DI-MSSM-81750 DoD M&S Accreditation Plan [4]
- DI-MSSM-81751 DoD M&S V&V Plan [5]
- DI-MSSM-81752 DoD M&S V&V Report [6]
- DI-MSSM-81753 DoD M&S Accreditation Report [7]

The DIDs define the data content, preparation instructions, format, and intended use for four VV&A documents. When it is necessary to obtain data, the applicable DID

must be listed on the Contract Data Requirements List (DD Form 1423). MIL-STD-3022 and the DIDs are available from the Acquisition Streamlining and Standardization Information System (ASSIST) at <http://assist.daps.dla.mil/>.

The DVDT automates the production of VV&A documentation in compliance with MIL-STD-3022 and enables the search and discovery of information about VV&A documents via the Global Information Grid (GIG) enterprise. The DVDT helps organizations (1) produce documents more efficiently by automatically populating common elements of a document with information entered by the producer when producing an earlier document (i.e., sharing common information across the documents); (2) organize the information in the documents; (3) output documents in a common format; and (4) make metadata about VV&A documents available to consumers across the GIG enterprise. These capabilities enable the MILCOM community to produce consistent VV&A information and to discover VV&A information about M&S used to support decisions about MILCOM and information processing systems.

CONCEPT OF OPERATIONS

The concept of operations in Figure 3 starts with the consumer in the upper right hand corner. A consumer has a need to use M&S; for example, to explore technical trade-offs in a complex communications architecture. The consumer employs the GIG to conduct a search for information about VV&A documents to locate resources that best meet requirements for the use of M&S.

Figure 3. Concept of Operations

VV&A metadata transferred from the DVDT and conforming to the M&S Community of Interest Discovery Metadata Specification (MSC DMS) [8] will be searchable

via the GIG. Based upon the information retrieved, the consumer is exposed to information that can inform the decision to reuse a legacy M&S "as is," to modify a legacy M&S, or to build a new M&S.

Starting in the upper left hand corner of Figure 3, the producer uses the DVDT to document VV&A planning, implementation, and reporting, e.g., of M&S used to represent MILCOM devices. The DVDT codifies VV&A business rules in XML and executes those rules. Upon registering and accessing the DVDT, the producer downloads a collection of interrelated XML-based files that are stored by the producer at the location of choice (e.g., on the producer's computer). These files represent the four templates formalized in MIL-STD-3022 [3]. These files use XML source data to produce printable documents. When the producer initiates a VV&A document project in the DVDT, certain VV&A metadata conforming to the MSC DMS is made available for search and discovery (e.g., contact information and project information). When a VV&A document is finalized and formally approved (i.e., signed), additional VV&A metadata can be made available to the enterprise for search and discovery.

DATA

The Net-Centric Data Sharing Strategy [9] is the guiding document for information sharing. The document defines net-centricity as "the realization of a networked environment, including infrastructure, systems, processes, and people, that enables a completely different approach to warfighting and business operations." The network foundation is the GIG, "the globally interconnected, end-to-end set of information capabilities, associated processes, and personnel for collecting, processing, storing, disseminating, and managing information on demand to warfighters, defense policymakers, and support personnel." Data assets addressed by the strategy include system files, databases, documents, official electronic records, images, audio files, websites, and data access services. Users and applications can search for and "pull" data as needed, or they can receive alerts when data to which they have subscribed is updated or changed. The goals of the strategy are to make data visible, accessible, institutionalized, understandable, trusted, interoperable, and responsive to user needs.

In the data sharing strategy, data assets are described by metadata to support discovery by users and applications. A standard set of metadata for discovering distributed resources is provided in the DoD Discovery Metadata Specification (DDMS) [10]. The DDMS states:

Data assets available on the Enterprise must be described with metadata, using the information elements defined in this document to permit discovery through the Enterprise Discovery capability. The DDMS defines a core set of elements that must be used to describe assets made visible to the Enterprise. Users (human and systems) that search the Enterprise will discover data assets that have been tagged and entered into catalogs or repositories that respond to search queries specified in terms of DDMS entries.

The DDMS design reflects a combination of a core layer of metadata with an extensible layer providing COI/domain-specific metadata. The Summary Content Category Set of the DDMS is specifically aimed at providing “content-related” details about data assets. Content metadata provides topics, keywords, context, and other content-related information; gives users and applications insight into the meaning and context of the data; and provides a basis for search engines to perform searches for data assets that address specific topics [9].

The data sharing strategy is being addressed through (1) self-organized Communities of Interest (COIs) for identification and maintenance of data; (2) metadata describing the data assets; and (3) GIG Enterprise Services supporting data tagging, sharing, searching, and retrieval. For example, the NetOps COI is operationalizing the GIG through network management, network defense, and content management. The DoD M&S COI is actively defining metadata for discovery of M&S resources. This group recently published the MSC DMS [8] built upon the information requirements of the DDMS [10].

The Net-Centric Data Sharing Strategy directs COIs to take the lead in establishing COI-specific metadata structures, defining community ontologies, cataloging data and metadata, and having members post data. A community ontology “provides the data categorization, thesaurus, key words, and/or taxonomy” that can be used to “increase semantic understanding and interoperability of the community data” [9, pp. 5-6]. Taxonomies “enhance discovery by providing a hierarchical means of searching for data while providing users and applications with additional insights about data assets by indicating their placement among other data assets” [9, p. 15]. Furthermore, COI-developed vocabularies will define terms used in describing data assets, and the thesauruses will identify related terms to assist translation services.

Such defined vocabularies, taxonomies, and ontologies can serve an important role in enhanced asset search and discovery in resource repositories.

Clearly, an important M&S resource is VV&A documentation as it provides evidence of the suitability of particular M&S for some intended use in the MILCOM and other communities.

As described earlier in the discussion of the concept of operations (Figure 3), the producer of standardized VV&A documentation will provide metadata that the DVDT will provide to the GIG enterprise for discovery. The data will be provided as XML documents for broad use by software applications. When a producer begins work on a VV&A document project, the tool will prompt for, store, and publish to the enterprise an initial set of metadata describing the VV&A document project as depicted in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Project-level XML Schema Documents

As the producer develops the various standard VV&A documents (Accreditation Plan, V&V Plan, V&V Report, and Accreditation Report) in Figure 5, the producer can direct the DVDT to extract and publish document-specific metadata describing the document itself as a new M&S resource.

This information can be updated as needed as document goes through its life cycle. Metadata describing M&S resources, such as VV&A documentation about M&S, is expected to be published to a future common M&S Catalog [11] currently under development.

The content of the VV&A documents is also stored as XML for processing by the DVDT software. The producer may choose to make the document content available through various DoD-, Service-, Community-specific catalogs, registries, and/or repositories.

Figure 5. Document-level XML Schema Documents

All standardized data about VV&A documentation that is stored to the enterprise will be stored as XML. XML schemas describing the structure and content of the various documents have been developed specifically for project-level metadata (Figure 4), document-specific metadata (Figure 5), and document content (Figure 5). The metadata schemas employ structures defined in the MSC DMS to ensure the community-required set of discovery metadata is provided in the standardized VV&A documentation metadata files. Work is continuing to develop VV&A taxonomy and ontology descriptions to enable future semantic search and query capabilities.

ARCHITECTURE

The DVDT's architecture provides a no-frills service to capture consistent information about the implementation of VV&A processes to determine confidence in the credibility of M&S results for an intended use. Using the DVDT should be easy for everyone engaged in VV&A activities since there are just four basic actions — register, download, produce, and update — as shown in Figure 6.

The producer will register the first time visiting the DVDT website. The registration process will solicit minimal information (e.g., contact information and project information) to assign a username and password. When a registered producer returns to the website, access will be achieved by username and password and/or a government Common Access Card or an External Certification Authority Public Key Infrastructure certificate.

Once registered, the producer initiates a VV&A document

project and downloads four XML VV&A schema documents that implement the four VV&A document templates in MIL-STD-3022 [3]. These schema documents are used by the organizations implementing the accreditation process and the verification and validation processes to record VV&A information. A fifth XML VV&A document downloaded provides help information and definition of common XML structures.

The DVDT populates the four VV&A documents with the common information identified in MIL-STD-3022 [3 - see Table I] when those documents are stored together. This capability will save producers time and money in the production of subsequent documents. Since the organization that produces the accreditation plan and report probably is different from the organization that produces the V&V plan and report, automatically sharing the common information across documents will depend on where the documents are stored. Coordination on the production of each of the individual documents by the different organizations involved in implementing the individual verification, validation, and accreditation processes will occur through the means used by the organizations involved (e.g., integrated digital environment, engineering environment, knowledge sharing environment, or sharing files through email). The decision where to retain the documents under control is left to the organizations producing the documents.

Figure 6. DVDT Architecture

Once a plan or report is finalized, approved, and signed, the producer updates the information in the M&S Catalog. This update adds information to the existing record in the M&S Catalog that was not available at the initiation of the VV&A document project.

Why is updating information about VV&A documents in the M&S Catalog important to the MILCOM consumer? Leveraging services is the answer. The M&S Catalog

provides the capability to search and discover information about M&S that have undergone VV&A when there is a need to use M&S to address a communications problem. Using the M&S Catalog, consumers will (1) find information about M&S that could meet their needs; (2) identify who "owns" the M&S and the VV&A documents; and (3) determine how to contact the owners.

All MILCOM domains (Sea, Land, Air, and Space) have access to the DVDT and the M&S Catalog. When the DVDT is used to produce VV&A documents, information about the existence of VV&A documents is shareable immediately across all MILCOM domains through the M&S Catalog via the GIG enterprise anywhere in the world and at anytime. Having VV&A document information readily available enables configuration of credible M&S environments to meet the needs of the MILCOM consumer.

ADDITIONAL INFORMATION

Information about this project and its products has been briefed at various M&S VV&A venues since 2007. The reader can learn more about the project's progress by perusing those already published papers and presentations [12-16].

SUMMARY

This paper informed the MILCOM community about the DoD M&S Project titled, "Standardized Documentation for VV&A." It provided information about MIL-STD-3022 [3] and the four associated DIDs [4-7] that are available in ASSIST. The paper described the ongoing efforts to establish XML VV&A schemas that enable the production of consistent VV&A documentation and the discovery of VV&A information. It also described the DVDT architecture and explained the four easy steps involved in using the DVDT - register, download, produce, and update. If the reader is interested in using the DVDT to support a VV&A implementation project, please contact any of the authors to obtain more information.

REFERENCES

- [1] Department of Defense: DoDI 5000.61, DoD Modeling and Simulation (M&S) Verification, Validation, and Accreditation (VV&A), May 2003.
- [2] Department of Defense. DoDD 5000.59, DoD Modeling and Simulation (M&S) Management. August 2008.
- [3] Department of Defense Modeling and Simulation

Coordination Office: MIL-STD-3022, Department of Defense Standard Practice Documentation of Verification, Validation, and Accreditation for Models and Simulations, January 2008.

- [4] Department of Defense Modeling and Simulation Coordination Office: DI-MSSM-81750 Department of Defense (DoD) Modeling and Simulation (M&S) Accreditation Plan, January 2008.
- [5] Department of Defense Modeling and Simulation Coordination Office: DI-MSSM-81751 Department of Defense (DoD) Modeling and Simulation (M&S) Verification and Validation (V&V) Plan, January 2008.
- [6] Department of Defense Modeling and Simulation Coordination Office: DI-MSSM-81752 Department of Defense (DoD) Modeling and Simulation (M&S) Verification and Validation (V&V) Report, January 2008.
- [7] Department of Defense Modeling and Simulation Coordination Office: DI-MSSM-81753 Department of Defense (DoD) Modeling and Simulation (M&S) Accreditation Report, January 2008.
- [8] Department of Defense Modeling and Simulation Coordination Office: M&S Community of Interest (COI) Discovery Metadata Specification (MSC-DMS), Version 1.0.1, January 2008.
- [9] Department of Defense Chief Information Officer: Net-centric Data Sharing Strategy, Washington DC, 9 May 2003.
- [10] Deputy Assistant Secretary of Defense: Department of Defense Discovery Metadata Specification (DDMS) (Version 1.4.1), Deputy Chief Information Office, 2007.
- [11] SPAWAR Systems Center Charleston: M&S Catalog Task 1: Metadata, Final Report, April 2008.
- [12] Broyles, D. H., Blais, C., and Stutzman, M.: "Automating Standardized Information for the Verification, Validation, and Accreditation Process: An Acquisition Community Sponsored M&S Project," Paper 07F-SIW-068, Proceedings of the Fall Simulation Interoperability Workshop, Simulation Interoperability Standards Organization, Orlando, Florida, September 2007.
- [13] Charlow, K., Broyles, D. H., Blais, C., and Stutzman, M.: "Acquisition M&S Community Sponsored M&S Project: Standardized Documentation for Verification, Validation, and Accreditation - A Status Report to the Systems Engineering Community," Paper 5431, Proceedings of the 10th Annual Systems Engineering Conference, National Defense Industrial Association, San Diego, California, October 2007.
- [14] Project Management Team: "DoD M&S Project:

Standardized Documentation for Verification, Validation, and Accreditation," Proceedings of the 2008 Department of Defense Modeling and Simulation Conference, Orlando, Florida, March 2008.

- [15] Charlow, K., Broyles, D. H., Blais, C., Daehler-Wilking, R., and Stutzman, M.: "Standardized Documentation for Verification, Validation, and Accreditation," Paper 08S-SIW-003, Proceedings of the 2008 Spring Simulation Interoperability Workshop, Simulation Interoperability Standards Organization, Providence, Rhode Island, April 2008.
- [16] Charlow, K., Blais, C., Daehler-Wilking, R., and Stutzman, M.: "Standardized Documentation for Verification, Validation, and Accreditation," Paper 08F-SIW-003, Proceedings of the 2008 Fall Simulation Interoperability Workshop, Simulation Interoperability Standards Organization, Orlando, Florida, September 2008.

ACRONYMS

ASSIST	Acquisition Streamlining and Standardization Information System (http://assist.daps.dla.mil/)
COI	Community of Interest
DDMS	DoD Discovery Metadata Specification
DID	Data Item Description
DoD	Department of Defense
DoDD	DoD Directive
DoDI	DoD Instruction
DVDT	DoD VV&A Documentation Tool
GIG	Global Information Grid
M&S	Modeling and simulation, models and simulations
M&S CO	M&S Coordination Office
M&S SC	M&S Steering Committee
MILCOM	Military Communications
MIL-STD	Military Standard
MOVES	Modeling, Virtual Environments, and Simulation
MSC DMS	M&S COI Discovery Metadata Specification
NMSO	Navy Modeling and Simulation Office
NPS	Naval Postgraduate School
V&V	Verification and validation
VV&A	Verification, validation, and accreditation
XML	Extensible Markup Language

AUTHORS

KEVIN CHARLOW is the Technical Operation Manager for the Enterprise C2 Engineering Division for the Space

and Naval Warfare Systems Center Charleston, South Carolina. He is the project team lead for the Standardized Documentation for Verification, Validation, and Accreditation Project. He has supported the Navy Modeling and Simulation Office for the last 6 years. Mr. Charlow has a Bachelor of Science degree in Computer Engineering from Clemson University and a Master of Business Administration degree from Webster University.

CURTIS BLAIS is a Research Associate with the Naval Postgraduate School (NPS) Modeling, Virtual Environments, and Simulation (MOVES) Institute. His primary areas of research and development include application of semantic web technologies to improve interoperability and for identifying and delivering valued information in network-centric environments such as the Global Information Grid. Mr. Blais earned Bachelor of Science and Master of Science degrees from the University of Notre Dame. He is currently a Ph.D. candidate in the MOVES program at NPS.

DAVID BROYLES is a scientist in the Command and Control Department at the Space and Naval Warfare Systems Center Charleston, South Carolina. He is the Architecture and Software Development Team Lead for the Standardized Documentation for VV&A Project. He has 13 years experience in software development in the areas of geographic information, document management, and accounting systems. He has supported NMSO for 5 years and led the software development of the Navy VV&A Documentation Tool.

MARCY STUTZMAN supports the DoD M&S Project, Standardized Documentation for Verification, Validation and Accreditation, as an Operations Research Analyst for the Northrop Grumman Corporation. She is the Policy, Guidance, and Standards Team Lead for that project. Additionally, she provides management and technical services to the Navy Modeling and Simulation Office (NMSO) VV&A Lead as a member of the NMSO VV&A Support Team. She served in the U.S. Army as a Senior Intelligence Research Analyst, Cryptologic Language Analyst, Reporter, and Voice Interceptor with five years duty at the National Security Agency. She is a member of the National Defense Industrial Association M&S Committee, the Simulation Interoperability Standards Organization, and the IEEE Standards Association. She has a Bachelor's degree from Indiana University and has provided M&S and VV&A support to the Department of Defense, Army, and Navy since 1990. Her hobby is birding.